

RESPOND

Working Papers

Global Migration: Consequences and Responses

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Conflicting conceptualisations of Europeanisation

Austria Country Report

Ivan Josipovic and Ursula Reeger

Institute for Urban and Regional Research
Austrian Academy of Sciences

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Any enquiries regarding this publication should be sent to us at: ursula.reeger@oeaw.ac.at

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List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	German	English
FPÖ	Freiheitliche Partei Österreichs	Freedom Party of Austria
Greens	Die Grünen – Die Grüne Alternative	The Greens – The Green Alternative
SPÖ	Sozialdemokratische Partei Österreichs	Social Democratic Party of Austria
ÖVP	Österreichische Volkspartei	Austrian People's Party

About the Project

RESPOND is a Horizon 2020 project, which aims at studying the multilevel governance of migration in Europe and beyond. The consortium is formed of 14 partners from 11 source, transit and destination countries and is coordinated by Uppsala University in Sweden. The main aim of this Europe-wide project is to provide an in-depth understanding of the governance of recent mass migration at macro, meso and micro levels through cross-country comparative research and to critically analyse governance practices with the aim of enhancing the migration governance capacity and policy coherence of the EU, its member states and third countries.

RESPOND studies migration governance through a narrative which is constructed along five thematic fields: (1) Border management and security, (2) Refugee protection regimes, (3) Reception policies, (4) Integration policies, and (5) Conflicting Europeanisation. Each thematic field between (1) and (5) is reflecting a juncture in the migration journey of refugees and designed to provide a holistic view of policies, their impacts and responses given by affected actors within.

In order to better focus on these themes, we divided our research question into work packages (WPs). The present report is concerned with the findings related to WP6, which focus specifically on public and political debates on Europeanisation in Austria.

Executive Summary

This working paper provides preliminary insights into public debates over Europeanisation and migration in Austria between 2011 and 2019. Based on a qualitative political claims analysis of 15 political speeches, 21 newspaper articles and nine stakeholder interviews, it provides an overview on how various actors problematized the EU, its Member States, and their policy-making and political targets in the realm of migration and asylum.

Early research results show a widely shared discontent over the EU's asylum system. But although there is disagreement over responsible actors and failed policy rationales, we also find broad consensus on the idea that reforms must happen at the European level (with right-wing populist politicians being a major exception). Thereby, the EU as a polity and as a set of rules, beliefs and cultures is filled with different meanings.

One line of argument asserts the EU as a power container that replaces and pools nation-state sovereignty, protecting external borders, even though this might implicitly occur to the detriment of human rights. Related positions tend to

- identify policy target groups as economic, illegal, or irregular migrants rather than refugees;
- point out the domestic population's scepticism towards immigration;
- consider the abrupt increase in the number of irregular migrant arrivals in 2015/2016 as a crisis resulting from lack of state power (i.e. to prevent asylum seekers' onward journey or to enforce return decisions);
- be permissive of national border controls if EU external borders are not be further securitized.

An opposing stance puts forward the claim of an EU which, at its core, is a peace and human rights project, and accordingly favours refugee dispersal policies and stronger harmonization of asylum policy, even if this might implicitly occur at the detriment of Member State self-interests. Related positions tend to

- emphasize the vulnerability of policy target groups as persons, who are fleeing war, persecution and exploitation;
- point out the reality of ethnic diversity within the domestic population;
- consider the crisis of 2015/2016 as a crisis resulting from Member States' self-interested actions and an insufficiently harmonized Common European Asylum System;
- favour active distribution and integration policies but show ambivalence regarding cooperation with third countries in the EU neighbourhood (i.e. EU-Turkey deal).

1. Introduction

Europeanisation is classically defined as “domestic change caused by European integration” (Vink, 2003, p.6). Since the early 1990s, the EU has established an elaborate regulatory framework on migration, asylum and border control. The Schengen Acquis, the Common European Asylum System (CEAS) and the cooperation on controlling external borders via FRONTEX represent some of the main pillars of this framework. In the past decade, new migration dynamics and most notably the so-called “refugee crisis” have challenged these regimes with many political stakeholders calling for urgent reform. In this working paper, we seek to offer preliminary insights into the way in which national politics and media make sense of the EU as a polity and as a set of rules, beliefs and cultures (Börzel & Risse, 2007; Mastenbroek & Kaeding, 2006).

Thus, the study focuses on the ideational dimension of Europeanisation by investigating political claims as well as claims made in Austrian media. We study the meaning that is attributed to policy issues in the area of migration, asylum, and borders and the role that the EU takes on as a policy-making entity. Clearly, the way in which social phenomena are constructed as political problems and the way in which substantive solutions and governance arrangements are envisioned strongly depends on the ideological stance of political and societal actors. As a heuristic tool, this paper deploys a conceptual dichotomy, distinguishing between two political identities, namely liberal and conservative Europeanisers.

Liberal Europeanisers are actors with a pluralistic vision of Europe as an “open society” who aim to incorporate ethnic diversity within the European project. They are in favour of an international humanitarian role for the EU. Here, the European ideal is built around a discourse of human rights based on the liberal platform of respect for individual dignity. In terms of refugee policies, they favour burden-sharing, quotas and reallocation.

Conservative Europeanisers promote a Europe based on a differentiation between the Judeo-Christian West and a non-Western “other”. Religion, ethnicity or race are considered central markers of difference. These actors are strongly focused on security concerns and favour a “fortress Europe” with a hard external border and strong police enforcement internally. They tend to be opposed to diversity and minority interests.

“Liberal and conservative Europeanisers” serve as broad conceptual categories, which will receive empirical attention in the course of WP6 of the Respond project. After providing insights into our methodological approach in section 2, we discuss Austrian party politics in section 3, domestic public media structures in section 4, and important migration related events and headlines. The following three sections provide first results from empirical research on political claims, media claims, and stakeholder claims.

2. Methodology

Our study builds on three types of data: political speeches (time period 2011-2019), media articles (time period: 2015-2019) and expert interviews (2018).

Chapter 6 is concerned with the analysis of political claims made by key political actors in relation to migration and EU-policy making. Therefore, we selected 15 speeches (see Appendix) by key politicians of four different parties covering a broad ideological spectrum (ÖVP, SPÖ, FPÖ, Greens). The central criterion were explicit references to the future of the EU and developments in the policy field of migration/asylum. The sample exclusively focused on federal-level politicians in government office or in parliamentary opposition. We selected the speeches through a key word Google search (“EU”+“Europe”+“Asyl*”/“Migration*”+[party name]). This initial sample consists of randomly chosen articles for each party and requires further theoretical sampling for theoretical saturation.

In chapter 7 we provide an overview of claims made in newspaper articles. In total, we selected 21 opinion articles from three different online daily newspaper outlets (7x liberal: Der Standard, 7x conservative: Die Presse, 7x centrist: Kurier; see Appendix). The articles were all opinion pieces/editorials, based on the assumption that this is a debate-focused genre encompassing longer discussions of an issue and revealing more of the ideational twist that a newspaper brings into social and political debate. We selected the articles through a key word search (“EU”+“Europe”+“Asyl*”/“Migration*”) within the search engines of each newspaper. Again, this initial sample consists of randomly chosen articles within each newspaper and requires further theoretical sampling for theoretical saturation.

The analysis of the speeches and media articles was based on a joint analytical grid that was established for the analysis of claims.¹

Categories of Analysis	Sub-Categories	Claims
Polity	1. EU	...
	2. Member State	
Actors	3. Object (talked about)	
	4. Subject (talked to)	
Propositions (migration related)	5. Diagnosis	
	6. Prognosis	

For each speech, we collected information according to the six dimensions listed with the grid:

¹ Codes were generate inductively and related to broader text passages (claims). For an example of the political speech analysis see Appendix.

Polity: On behalf of what (EU/ Member State) is the actor speaking?

1. How do they thematize/problematize the EU/ the member state (self-understanding)?
2. What is demanded from the EU/Member State regarding integration/coordination in governance?

Actors: Consideration of the subject (the one that the political actor is talking to, for example “our society”) and the object (the one that the political actor is talking about, for example “refugees”).

3. How is the object problematized?
4. What is explicitly demanded from the subject?

Propositions: Consideration of policy rationale regarding migration

5. Diagnosis: What kind of problem is identified? How are the previous measures evaluated?
6. Prognosis: What types of action/policy are demanded as solution?

The goal regarding both political speech analysis and media analysis is to explore the broad variety of ideological positions and argumentative patterns.

In section 8 we discuss points of views shared by experts working in the field of asylum and immigrant integration. Due to the outbreak of the Corona virus pandemic, we were not able to collect new data. Instead, we drew on expert interview material that we had gathered in 2018 for the purpose of RESPOND WPs 2-5.

3. Party-Political Structures in Austria: History and Developments since 2011²

Since 1945, Austria has been a federal, representative democratic republic. Its federal character derives from a division of legislative, executive and judicial powers between the federal level, called *Bund*, and the nine provinces that are called *Länder*. Since Austria's accession to the EU in 1995, certain competences have been delegated to the supranational level. The system of government is characterized by a mix of presidential and parliamentary elements, whereby the former is rather weakly pronounced, which leads to it being classified as semi-presidentialism. The parliament has two chambers, the National Council with 183 seats and the Federal Council that assembles delegates from the provinces.

The formation of the federal government has historically been rather atypical for a parliamentary system, as Austria displays a longstanding tradition of grand coalitions between the social democrats (Sozialdemokratische Partei Österreichs – SPÖ) and the conservatives (Österreichische Volkspartei – ÖVP) (Pelinka & Rosenberger, 2007). A reason for this is the political culture characteristic of consociational democracies. In the case of Austria, the broad involvement of (non-winning) political minorities strongly evolved around the conflictual experiences of the First Republic (1918-1934) and the aim of conciliation of the class cleavage between capital and labour. It is also in this context that Austrian Corporatism emerged with a continuously high degree of coordination between business and labour stakeholders as well as institutionalized bargaining practices (Pernicka & Helfer, 2015).

Immigration and immigrant integration experienced a new level of politicization from the 1990s onwards. This was not only due to the refugee influx from the former Yugoslavia but also as a result of increased partisan interest in the topic. The oppositional liberal-left Greens (Die Grünen) and the right-wing populist Freedom Party (Freiheitliche Partei Österreichs – FPÖ) began to address migration from diametrically opposed ideological positions. This exerted pressure on the two established parties to position themselves more comprehensively and pass new legislation (Gruber, 2014).

Even more, the ÖVP gradually sought to challenge the FPÖ's issue ownership by institutionalizing the policy field of immigrant integration within the government offices held by its ministers (Gruber & Rosenberger, 2016). Initially located within Ministry of Interior, integration matters were later incorporated into the Ministry of Foreign Affairs, Europe and Integration. In 2002, the federal government introduced an Integration Ministry under the lead of an ÖVP minister.

Within the time period under consideration (2011 until April 2020), Austria had four different partisan constellations within federal government. Between 2011 and 2017, the federal government consisted of the historically dominant grand coalition between ÖVP and SPÖ. As result of the so-called refugee crisis, the 2017 national elections can be considered a critical juncture in the context of party politics and migration governance.

This might particularly account for the transformations of the conservative party (ÖVP), where the role of current chancellor Sebastian Kurz and his political vision setting an emphasis on

² Parts of chapter 3 were adopted from the WP1 Country Report “Legal and Policy Framework in Austria” (Josipovic & Reeger, 2018) and updated where necessary.

order and security in relation to immigration replaced the traditional primacy of economic concerns in the ÖVP. As Bodlos & Plescia (2018) showed, the ÖVP mentioned immigration in more press releases during the electoral campaign 2017 than ever before. While the topic's share among other policy issues was at an average of 1.6% between 1999 and 2013, it peaked at 7.6% in 2017 (Bodlos & Plescia, 2018, p. 1357). The party adopted much of the positions of the populist right wing party FPÖ when it comes to immigration and integration (ibid., p. 1357). Coupled with intra-party restructuring that introduced new staff (putting an emphasis on experts) at the federal level and a new political branding strategy, the ÖVP managed to increase its approval rates within a short period of time from an average of 20% to a stable 33%, even after entering the new coalition.³

For the social democratic SPÖ and the Greens, the immigration issue proved to be highly divisive. At the 2017 election, the SPÖ remained relatively constant at an all-time low of 26.9%, while the Greens dropped out of parliament after 31 years with only 3.8%. For the SPÖ, immigration issues led to new debates over an ideological division. On the one hand, the former defense minister together with the regional Burgenland division sought a more restrictive approach towards immigration and immigrant integration. On the other hand, a liberal or progressive wing was often identified in the circles around the former chancellor Christian Kern.

The populist right wing FPÖ, which held an issue ownership on immigration over decades, tamed its rhetoric during the 2017 elections. While this might stand in opposition to party internal structures (members belonging to dueling fraternities caused media attention during regional elections), the party broadened its topical spectrum with the creation of a new economic program and largely avoided controversial comments during the election period (Bodlos & Plescia, 2018). The FPÖ, which had over decades shifted the entire political discourse on immigration towards the right, emerged as a major winner following the “refugee crisis”.

From December 2017 until May 2019, the federal government consisted of a coalition between the conservative ÖVP and the FPÖ. As a result of political scandal caused by FPÖ politicians, the coalition broke apart, and following a non-confidence vote in the National Council, an expert government took over office from June 2019 to January 2020. The snap elections of 2019 made the ÖVP the strongest party in parliament with around 37 percent of the votes. They entered into a coalition with the Greens in January 2020, despite conflicting stances on migration issues.

³ Source: <https://neuwal.com/wahlumfragen/>.

4. Media Structure and the Question of Europeanisation

The print media in Austria is characterized by a very high degree of concentration. This means that a few media houses dominate the market. One of the largest companies is Mediaprint, which was founded in 1988 by the daily newspapers "Kronen Zeitung" and "Kurier" (also linked by the German Funke Group). The second major competitor is the Styria Media Group with papers such as "Die Presse" and "Kleine Zeitung". Eventually, the quality newspaper "Der Standard" was founded in 1988 and its majority owner is the Bronner Family Private Foundation.

Plasser & Palaver (2017) point out how Austria has only 16 daily newspapers, which is a relatively low number compared to other countries with a similar size of population (Finland around 50, Denmark over 30). Kronen Zeitung has by far the highest reach. It accounted for 30% of the total circulation of Austrian daily newspapers in 2017 and is therefore comparable to the German Bild-Zeitung or the British Sun.⁴ *Die Presse* and *Der Standard* represent the two major titles of nationwide quality press, they reached 4.3% and 5.4% respectively (Plasser & Palaver, 2017). With regard to online media, derStandard.at achieved a monthly reach of 38.6% among Internet users for the individual offers in the fourth quarter of 2019, while diePresse.com counts 13.2% and KURIER ONLINE-Medien 37.1% (ÖWA, 2019).

The consequence of this concentration is the narrowing of editorial attention to selective thematic areas, and campaign journalism with a preference for certain positions of individual political actors (Plasser & Palaver, 2017).

Considering the worldview spectrum of Austrian print media, *Der Standard* and *Die Presse*, both generally considered quality newspapers, point to opposing directions. The former is centre-left orientated and the latter conservative in socio-political terms and (neo-)liberal in economic terms. Kurier is considered a centrist paper moving between liberal and recently more conservative positions.

In Austria, every newspaper has to disclose its editorial concept (Blattlinie) (in terms of a general world view), at regular intervals. These can be found on the homepage of the Association of Austrian Newspapers (VÖZ).

According to the 2016 (VÖZ, 2017, own translation):

1. "DER STANDARD" is a liberal medium. It is independent of political parties, institutions and interest groups and is aimed at all readers who place high demands on thorough and comprehensive reporting as well as on well-founded, appropriate commentary in the fields of economics, politics, culture and society. "DER STANDARD" and derStandard.at join forces for the preservation and promotion of parliamentary democracy and republican political culture, for constitutional goals in the rejection of political extremism and totalitarianism, for strengthening the economic competitiveness of the country according to the principles of a social

⁴ Due to its tabloid character, our methodical approach, which is focused on claims and arguments delivered in longer opinion pieces, has not been adequate for an analysis of Kronen Zeitung. Generally, Kronen Zeitung is considered to be a tabloid paper with alternating positions depending on issues – in the context immigration and Europeanization it tends to align with right-wing populist positions.

market economy, for tolerance towards all ethnic and religious communities, for equal rights for all citizens and all federal provinces of the Republic of Austria” (VÖZ, 2017, own translation)

2. “Die Presse” represents conservative-liberal views at a high level, independent of the political parties. It advocates parliamentary democracy based on the multi-party system and the rule of law. “Die Presse” is committed to the principles of social justice while maintaining the personal responsibility of the citizen, to the protection of private property while respecting his obligations to society, to the principles of the social market economy, to free entrepreneurial initiative and to competition for performance. It defends the fundamental freedoms and human rights and fights against all efforts which are likely to endanger these freedoms and rights or the democratic social order based on the rule of law. “Die Presse” considers it a journalistic professional duty to inform its readers objectively and as completely as possible about all events of general interest. The daily newspaper “Die Presse” regards it as its duty and inalienable right to comment and criticise” (VÖZ, 2017, own translation).
3. “The political (basic intellectual) direction of “KURIER” is determined by the editor.
 1. The “KURIER” is an independent Austrian daily newspaper.
 2. The editorial office therefore keeps itself free from all direct and indirect influences of political parties and interest groups.
 3. The “KURIER” is unreservedly committed to the integrity, statehood and federal structure of the Republic of Austria and its constructive contribution to the process of European integration.
 4. The “KURIER” is committed to parliamentary democracy and the rule of law. Through its journalistic activities it promotes their further development. It fights constructively against abuses in democratic life.
 5. The “KURIER” considers itself an instrument of democratic opinion-forming in the sense of comprehensive freedom of information.
 6. The “KURIER” advocates the greatest possible freedom for citizens within the framework of the law. He therefore affirms a free social order and its orderly development, which excludes any extremism.
 7. The “KURIER” supports the idea and system of the social market economy with consideration of ecology.
 8. The guiding principle of its journalistic activities is the deepening of tolerance in all areas of life, the defence of freedom of conscience and respect for all religious communities” (VÖZ, 2017, own translation).

5. Headlines and Events Impacting on Asylum/Migration Discourse since 2011

A brief look back at major narratives during the past decades shows that the arrival of large numbers of political refugees from Hungary (180,000 asylum seekers in 1956/57), the former Czechoslovakia (160,000 persons in 1968/69) and from Poland at the beginning of the 1980s was mainly perceived very positive in the public and the media. One of the reasons for this was the fact that most of them went on to other destinations seeing Austria only as a first safe haven and a transit opportunity. The Austrian public expressed enormous sympathy for refugees from behind the Iron Curtain, whom they saw as victims of communism (Fassmann & Reeger 2012, p. 78).

The recruitment of large numbers of guest workers started at the beginning of the 1960s and went on until 1973 (first oil price shock). As the term “guest” implies, these migrants were welcomed most of all by the economy as a source of wealth, but not as a part of Austrian society. With the start of economic recession at the beginning of the 1970s, public opinion about immigration and guest workers changed dramatically. While people from (the former) Yugoslavia and Turkey were tolerated in times of good economic performance, the public increasingly perceived them as a threat, and as those who would take advantage of the welfare system (Fassmann & Reeger 2012).

Two major events, namely the Fall of the Iron Curtain and the wars in the Balkans at the beginning of the 1990s, had a massive impact on international migration numbers to Austria. These events led to a polarization in public opinion and changed narratives completely. An anti-immigration referendum called “Austria first” launched by the right wing FPÖ (Freedom Party Austria) attracted more than 400,000 Austrians as signatories. By contrast, the “sea of lights”, a public event in the heart of Vienna, brought 300,000 persons to demonstrate against racism and xenophobia (Fassmann & Reeger 2012).

In its recent history, Austria can be defined as an “unwilling immigration country” with polarized stances towards immigrants and a shift in narratives from liberalisation to increased rejection.

During the time period under consideration, there was a pronounced shift in major discourses on migration in Austria. Known for the comparatively sceptical attitudes of the population *vis-a-vis* newcomers (as proven by several waves of the European Social Survey), the discourse came to focus mainly on EU mobility and immigration from the “new” Eastern European accession states as well as on problems related to integration in general until around 2010 and then turned to issues of refugees and asylum as of 2014 – a topic that remained valid until the beginning of 2020 when Covid-19 “took over”. With the complete closure of all borders, immigration disappeared as an issue and will only reappear in public and political discourse once the borders are completely open again.

In a study aiming at identifying the most dominant frames in the coverage of refugee and asylum issues during the peak of the “refugee crisis” (January 2015 to January 2016), Greussing and Boomgaarden (2017) built on more than 10,500 newspaper articles from three quality papers and three tabloids. Due to the thirteen month investigation period, the authors were able to analyse variations in frames in different stages of the ongoing arrival of refugees. Regarding these portrayals of asylum and refugees and their change over time, the authors confirm parallels to frames compared to other Western mass media discourses, on the one

hand, and no pronounced differences between frames in quality papers and tabloids (with the exception of the “criminality” frame), on the other. They argue that there is a pronounced “persistence of stereotyped interpretations of refugee and asylum issues, even in times of major humanitarian and political crises” (Greussing and Boomgaarden 2017, p. 1764).

Key events and discourses include the death of 71 persons in the morning of 26 August, 2015 on Austrian territory near the village of Parndorf. They were found suffocated in a refrigerated truck on a motorway near the Hungarian border. Packed on only 13m², 59 men, eight women and four children from Afghanistan, Iraq, Iran and Syria who had started out in this truck from the Hungarian town of Morahalom near the Hungarian-Serbian border had tried to reach Western Europe mostly with the help of smugglers. This event triggered a lot of public and media reactions ranging from the Austrian President, to ecclesial dignitaries and parts of civil society all over the country which led to a demonstration involving 20,000 persons to commemorate the victims of Parndorf. This was an outstanding event reflected in societal and media discourse as it transported the “refugee crisis” from more remote areas in the Balkans and the Mediterranean right into the Austrian daily life. It introduced a humanitarian perspective to debates over external migration.

In early September 2015, the Austrian Minister of the Interior adopted a pragmatic approach, announcing that the Dublin Regulation would only be applied according to the principle of proportionality. On 5 September, several thousand refugees from Hungary crossed the Austrian border and then travelled on towards Germany for the most part. Poor reception conditions in Hungary, and mediatized images from Budapest Train Stations triggered a wave of solidarity and support for refugees arriving at Vienna Westbahnhof. This was accompanied with a massive march for refugee rights under the title of "Being human in Austria" and a solidarity concert "Voices for Refugees".

There is a strong connection between German and Austrian media when it comes to the interpretation of events and their coverage over migration. The pictures of the dead body of Alan Kurdi on a sandy beach triggered a lot of empathy, while the sexual assaults on New Year's Eve in Cologne at the end of the same year yielded a sense of threat. In the course of time, broader societal support towards asylum seekers declined and in part even turned into rejection over time (Müller & Rosenberger, 2017, p. 118). Today, large parts of public discourse neglect the humanitarian dimension and focus on implications for the social system and criminality. Notions of building a “fortress Europe” and the political will to keep refugees from coming to Austria add to this considerably.

6. Political Speeches

6.1 Polity: Problematizing the EU and inter-state relations

Across all political speeches that were analysed, a widely shared assumption was that political issues surrounding migration and particularly the so-called refugee crisis of 2015 touched upon core structural conditions for the future development of the EU. However, what this precisely means varied greatly across different parties. The right-wing populist H.C. Strache, for example, argues that the 2015 crisis represented yet another stage of the EU gradually “abolish[ing] itself” (S4⁵). He criticizes the calls for “more Europe” and insists that the nation-state has to ensure that existing laws are respected. For him, it is about finding partners at the EU level that share the ambition of a reduced European Union that is confined to its task of maintaining peace among its member states. Upon entering the federal government in late 2017, Herbert Kickl from the FPÖ actively asserted Austria’s role as a restrictive immigration country that sought to find partners for a paradigmatic shift in European asylum and migration policy. He particularly mentioned Denmark as a partner in the EU, but also non-EU members in the Western Balkans.

In 2017, the conservative politician Sebastian Kurz (ÖVP), while the foreign minister at the time, also bemoaned that the EU was overloaded with too many competences, leading to an excessive amount of regulations (AT10-2017-Kurz). In this vein, he fostered the traditional ÖVP credo of subsidiarity. According to him, the failure of the EU to protect its external borders called up national governments to re-introduce intra-Schengen border controls. Such controls would erode the idea of a unified Europe, yet he presented them as a necessity simply resulting from “the wrong refugee policy and of the euphoria of all those who, at that time, stood up for unrestricted admission [of refugees]” (AT10-2017-Kurz). In this regard, Kurz also called upon the nation state to react if intra-EU mobility was wrongly interpreted by EU citizens as immigration into national welfare systems and further argued that Austria had to react to such abuses of the freedom of movement.

An opposing stance was taken by the Green’s Eva Glawischnig, who pointed to the EU as a peace and human rights project with the right to asylum at its core. She contextualized her speech within the 25th anniversary of the fall of the Berlin Wall in 2014. According to her, illegalizing the entry of persons seeking for asylum, be it at the external border or within the EU, contradicts the spirit of the EU. In this vein, her colleague Alev Korun (AT15-2015-Korun) pointed to the lack of solidarity of Austria and other EU members with the southern countries like Italy, Greece and Spain who are systemically overburdened. She argued that Member States should not exclusively call upon the EU when they are affected by a problem themselves, but rather act in solidarity.

The SPÖ, by contrast, which was in government during the peak of the so-called refugee crisis, supported a joint European externalization strategy through the EU-Turkey deal. For the then chancellor Werner Faymann (AT14-2015-Faymann), it was about joining forces with Germany and other member states who were willing to find European solutions and to tackle the root causes of increasing immigrant numbers. Meanwhile, Faymann’s successor Christian Kern

⁵ The abbreviation S4 stands for the fourth speech we selected for this analysis. Please find a full list of the selected speeches in the appendix.

called for reform of the European Union, arguing that multiple crises, including that of Brexit, were catalysts for this development (AT2-2017-Kern).

6.2 Actors: constructing target groups and domestic audiences

The FPÖ generally constructed a negative picture of asylum seekers, delegitimizing their claim to asylum, not only by drawing on their qualities as a policy target group but also by claiming that the government failed to conduct identifications of those persons who arrived in 2015 (AT4-2015-Strache). Asylum was tightly linked to illegal migration, and migrants were repeatedly placed in a context facing widespread suspicion and security concerns. H.C. Strache for example argued: “If we also address the issue of asylum, temporary asylum was an essential principle. We must therefore also resolutely fight against ‘asylum abuse’ and ‘illegal migration’. And here we have stated on the whole that asylum procedures must of course be handled more efficiently, and that in the future, they must also be carried out more quickly and more efficiently, and that the return of so-called asylum swindlers must also be carried out consistently” (AT13-2017-Strache). In a context of procedural restrictions for asylum seekers, his colleague Herbert Kickl turns the classic slogan of solidarity with refugees upside down by “demand[ing] solidarity from those who came to us” (AT7-2018-Kickl). Accordingly, he pointed to the social support provided to asylum seekers and refugees in Austria, arguing that least what one could expect was cooperation on the establishment of their identity.

A similar rhetoric can be found in the speeches of ÖVP politicians. In contrast to the FPÖ, the former minister of interior Johanna Mikl-Leitner made it her personal goal to provide protection to persons that were persecuted, thereby primarily legitimizing instances where a claim to asylum could be made (AT5-2012-Mikl-Leitner). However, her immediate second goal was to “declare a permanent fight against asylum abuse” (AT5-2012-Mikl-Leitner). Closing legal loopholes for asylum abuse is a precondition for her, “to help those who needed help” (AT5-2012-Mikl-Leitner). In this regard she delegitimized the presence of asylum claimants by pointing to their journey via “safe third countries” for example or by linking them to criminal activities in Austria. Furthermore, Mikl-Leitner tried to relativize claims of the FPÖ that refugees were a threat to domestic employees by pointing out legal restrictions with regard to labour market access of asylum seekers. Instead, she argued “that economic refugees were blocking our asylum system”. In a 2017 speech, Sebastian Kurz (ÖVP) pointed to the past generation of immigrants as a target group population that lacked integration, thus calling for a “basic social consensus” (AT1-2017-Kurz) of norms and values that need to be conveyed to them.

Christian Kern (AT2-2017-Kern) from the SPÖ by contrast pointed to ethnic diversity as a positive aspect of Austrian society. He used the example of Austria’s football team with players of diverse ethnic backgrounds but all playing under the Red-White-Red flag. With regard to refugees he pointed to their vulnerability by citing a personal encounter with a Yazidi girl who lost her family before she came to Austria. Also he explicitly addressed the need to be cautious about the way “we” referred to migrants and refugees. He argued: “In this discussion, we should pay the utmost attention to creating a construction where ‘we’ and ‘the others’ are concerned: the ‘inferior’, the ‘undesirable’. The ones we don’t want in our country” (AT2-2017-Kern). Nonetheless, he too emphasizes the importance of integration in terms of learning the German language, “our values”, and how to make a contribution to society. Most notably, Kern referred to domestic audiences as carrying legitimate worries and fears with regard to the topic

of immigration. But, he continued, “it is also clear to us that we cannot answer these questions with populist recipes and slogans” (AT2-2017-Kern). In this regard, he mentions criminal immigrants in the context of a “false tolerance”. Accordingly, diversity must not allow migrants “fleeing into parallel worlds”, most notably extremist religious communities. Instead, the state would have to convey basic liberal norms, such as equality between men and women. In this vein, he sought to advance the argument that some concerns of right-wing voters were legitimate but that the Social Democracy offered “real” policy solutions. In this context, he also referred to domestic audiences as having humanitarian obligations towards refugees. In a 2015 speech, Kern’s predecessor Werner Faymann emphasized at the peak of the so-called refugee crisis that the question of refugees and security concerns like terrorism should not be mixed up. Accordingly, “Refugees also flee from terrorists” (AT14-2015-Faymann).

The Greens generally tend to emphasize the vulnerability of refugees pointing to their exposure to war and persecution as well as their inhumane treatment along the EU’s external borders. Eva Glawischnig for example argues: “In other words, if a family from an area controlled by IS has managed to get on very dangerous paths and found the way across the Mediterranean, then there is a great chance that this family in front of our walls, which Europe has raised, is drowning. That is, I say in all openness, no longer tolerable, for all of us no longer bearable!” (AT3-2015-Glawischnig).

Summing up, we find that both the FPÖ and the ÖVP place a strong emphasis on the identity of those who are newly arriving to Austria. However, while the FPÖ places a general suspicious and disbelief across all asylum seekers, the ÖVP divides between what they consider genuine asylum seekers and labour migrants who are blocking the asylum system. By contrast, the Greens point out the vulnerability of refugees and criticize the legal and practical hurdles that the EU has set up to prevent people from immigrating. The SPÖ takes the most differentiated or ambivalent stance by highlighting how ethnic diversity is already party of our social reality on the one hand and underscoring the need to establish clear rules for integration on the other.

6.3 Policy propositions: diagnosis of former decisions and proposition of new solutions

In November 2015, H.C. Strache from the FPÖ, then in opposition, argued that the government failed in the management of the crisis. He pointed at 430,000 people entered the country or were allowed to travel further towards Germany and argued that the government failed to follow its obligations towards its citizens in “ensuring the safety, peace and order of your own people” (AT4-2015-Strache). Upon entering government, Herbert Kickl from the FPÖ (AT7-2018-Kickl) who became Interior Minister in late 2017, argued that “those who believed that we could solve refugee problems of other continents in Austria and Europe were sitting on an illusion”. He proposed that Austria together with its European partners, had to ensure “that aid and support for those who had to flee, were persecuted, and were as close as possible to the scene of events. It [aid in third country] is cheaper, it is fairer for those who had to flee. And, above all, it was something that our own people expected of us” (AT7-2018-Kickl). Furthermore, he favoured increased involvement in border control cooperation through a strengthened FRONTEX mandate. At the peak of the crisis of 2015, when the federal government began to build a border fence, Kickl’s colleague Strache used the metaphor of a house in relation to the nation-state: “In Slovenia, a fence is currently being built with the support of the Austrians. Suddenly the fence is possible! - Of course, this is possible anyway, I say, because every

house has a garden fence so that not every unauthorized person could enter the property, and you do not open up doors and windows so that any unauthorized person can get into the apartment or into the house. Of course, this is necessary to prevent illegal entry, and in the end this is what we have to ensure” (AT4-2015-Strache).

Sebastian Kurz (S1/S10) and Johanna Mikl-Leitner (AT11-2015-Mikl-Leitner) (ÖVP) sought to present themselves as advocates of realism, namely a political approach that confronted idealists with “the truth” (AT1-2017-Kurz) that the levels of immigration were too high. Kurz for example argued: “I can remember being criticized because I did not like to have a party at Westbahnhof [train station where volunteers supported refugees arriving via Hungary]. And I can remember that the climax of the criticism was when Hanni [Johanna Mikl-Leitner] and I tried to close the Western Balkans route.” According to Kurz, his political opponents would try to push him into the “right-wing corner” (AT1-2017-Kurz). Despite being part of the government during crisis of 2015, the ÖVP sought to distinguish itself from its coalition partner SPÖ but also from the other EU member states. Kurz criticized “waving through” (AT1-2017-Kurz) refugees across borders to Central Europe as the crisis policy, and argued that he as the minister of foreign affairs managed to “close the Western Balkans route” (AT1-2017-Kurz). Distribution policies by contrast, were considered illusionary approaches at the face of high numbers of immigrants. During her time as interior minister, Johanna Mikl-Leitner advocated accelerated asylum procedures as well as more efficient return policies for rejected asylum seekers.

In 2015, the oppositional Greens heavily criticised what they considered a “refugee defence policy” (AT3-2015-Glawischnig) by the federal government and they sought to align their policies with civil society protests to support the development of a humane refugee policy in Austria. Eva Glawischnig pointed to the government’s repeated support of extending the FRONTEX mandate, which as she argued, only protected borders but not people. In this vein, she also pointed out how Austria had never supported any sea rescuing operations in the Mediterranean. Another point of critique were the safe third country policies, and the EU’s cooperation with the Libyan government: “I do not know how one can come up with the idea - of these states in their present condition - to outsource what is actually our responsibility. It would be our responsibility to have an open door for refugees, to review their asylum applications and to give them, if they have a refugee reason, also a welcome and a chance for a new life.” (AT3-2015-Glawischnig) Glawischnig’s colleague Alev Korun (AT4-2015-Strache) furthermore argues that the Dublin Agreement could no longer be upheld: “It did not work, and those who paid the bill were Italy, Greece and Spain, and above all the refugees affected.” (AT4-2015-Strache)

The SPÖ, while also supporting a “humane” policy approach (AT14-2015-Faymann) was confronted with the situation of carrying responsibility in government during the period of 2011 - 2017. Thus it combined its humanitarian stance with a demand for organisation and order. At the European level, Werner Fayman accordingly supported the EU-Turkey Deal, despite human rights concerns: “But that also means working together with Turkey. Which is not entirely pleasant under certain circumstances, because the human rights situation in Turkey is not perfect either” (AT14-2015-Faymann). Upon his political resignation in 2016, he pointed to positive policy legacy that he left behind: “Austria has also achieved something. Austria granted asylum rights to more than 90,000 people last year. At the beginning of this year it was clear that the European solutions from securing the EU’s external borders to fair distribution were not ready. They did not exist. It was clear that it is right to continue to support this course

politically. But it would have been irresponsible not to take our own measures. Not because they are better. Not because you turn things around - for some reason. But because reality demands that you, as a responsible person, also assume responsibility” (AT5-2012-Mikl-Leitner).

6.4 Discussion: Liberal vs Conservative Europeanisers?

The position of Liberal Europeanisers was taken unsurprisingly by social democratic and Green politicians first and foremost. These politicians indeed shared ambitions for a humanitarian and ethnically diverse European Union. Yet, further research has to investigate diverging stances with regard to how ethnical diversity was perceived, and whether political actors envisioned multiculturalist or integrationist paradigms of refugee reception. Similarly, it appears worthwhile to study how immigration was conceptualized in the context of the transformation of welfare states, particularly by social democratic actors. What kind of social justice do these actors envision in the context of humanitarianism: sufficiency in terms of an absolute social minimum for refugees or equality in terms of a social levelling up relative to privileged groups? Finally, while Liberal Europeanisers generally favoured EU distribution policies and intervening into migration root causes, it is important to further investigate the precise motives and discursive patterns of legitimization. Are refugees distributed for the sake of their wellbeing, or due to negative attitudes among the domestic population? Likewise, the Austrian case showed liberal divisions with regard to the question of externalization of migration control. Scholars need to investigate under which circumstances deals with third countries over refugee re-admission or re-location are considered viable and ethically sound solution.

The position of Conservative Europeanisers was taken primarily by conservative and right-wing populist actors, as our sample showed. These actors argued in favour of a tightening of security measures along national and external Schengen borders. However, there were clear distinctions to be made with regard to the division of political competences between the EU and its Member States. Further research needs to study how classical conservative and right-wing agendas such as security are translated into the EU multi-level setting: should left-overs of national sovereignty on border control be further pooled at the European level, should national border control be upheld in the light of subsidiarity if external border protection fails, or should competences on migration and border control all together be withdrawn from the EU? Another important aspect were differences with regard to how the policy target group was discursively constructed. While all Conservative Europeanisers strongly engaged in discourses of “othering”, there were still different ways of connecting notions of “the refugee”, “the illegal migrant”, “the economic migrant” in order to advance certain policies.

7. Circulation of Claims in Mainstream Media

7.1 What do the EU and its member states stand for? Conflicting values and identities

Positions relating to the polity of the EU, Austria, or other Member States were mainly expressed in terms of values and identities that are attached to these entities. Who is the EU, who is Austria and what do they stand for? The three newspapers that were analysed showed a variety of different interpretations regarding these questions.

On the conservative spectrum, the EU was referred to as “a strange construct” (AT-2015-P1), wherein Member States have committed to shared values and shared sovereignty in certain policy areas, without having paid enough attention to controls and sanctions upon failure to comply. Here, ceding sovereignty to the supranational level is largely associated with the need for a stronger EU external border. Tightened security measures at the external borders were seen as a precondition to return to free movement in the Schengen Area. In this vein, one author argued that “Europe’s moral-imperialism needed to be trashed” (AT-2015-P6). Arguably, the EU and particularly leftist elites believing the EU’s soft-power of moral supremacy would leave the dirty work of EU-border protection to “Islamic autocrats” (reference to EU-Turkey Deal). The undercurrent was that EU politicians should be self-conscious actors instead of suffering “panic attacks when they see the images of robustly secured external borders [...]” (AT-2015-P6).

On the liberal spectrum, the political project of “Fortress Europe” was criticized. It is considered an extension of nationalistic domestic politics. One author called for a return to the EU foreign policy soft power: “In order to take the wind out of the populist narrative of demarcation and withdrawal, we must make it clear that openness and global commitment made Europe strong” (AT-2016-ST5). By contrast, another author in *Der Standard* (AT-2018-ST2) argued that the only way in which Europe can return to its core values of tolerance, liberalism and diversity is to become a fortress. Arguably, mass migration would lead to right-wing populist backlashes, particularly in Eastern Europe which had less experience with “immigration from other cultures” (AT-2018-ST2).

A common undercurrent found across different positions was that the EU was a construct of solidarity between Member States, but it failed to deliver such solidarity in the context of migration governance. A commonly argued symptom of this development was the reintroduction of national border controls in the Schengen Area. An author from *Kurier* (AT-2015-K3) located the reason for a lack of solidarity in right-wing populism that was spreading across the continent. He argued that “instead of a fair distribution of refugees, the supposedly solidarity based and united peace union is once again governed by the fist of the strongest” (AT-2015-K3). A commentator from *Die Presse* (AT-2015-P2) by contrast considered the lack of solidarity as a result of a divide between liberal societal elites and the working class, which resented further immigration. Another author from *Kurier* (AT-2015-K2) sought to provide a positive example by pointing out how Austria admitted many thousands of refugees during the Balkan Wars. In the context of 2015 crisis, he argued “Europe needs more of this spirit of solidarity with the stranded. The more countries deliver this spirit, the more the new refugee drama will be politically acceptable to everyone” (AT-2015-K2).

Regarding Austria, the same author (and also P2) criticized that despite several historic moments since 1945 that proved the country's liberal attitude towards refugees, it was now failing to live up to this virtue amidst the 2015 crisis. Austria was also criticised for its role as a "solo runner" (Alleingänger) due to multilateral cooperation with Western Balkan countries that took place outside of EU arenas (AT-2018-P4). During Austria's EU presidency in 2018, one author pointed to the "denial of reality" in the context of Austria's repeated mantra of shutting down borders. According to him, a globalized world requires a certain degree of permeability when it comes managing migration and borders. Under ÖVP exterior minister and later chancellor Sebastian Kurz, Austria was considered to have departed from the paradigm of "welcome culture" that is associated with Sweden and Germany (AT-2017-P5).

Two other EU-Member States that were most often referenced were Hungary, as an example of nation-state sovereignty or blind right-wing populism, and Germany, as an example of humanitarianism or naïve liberalism. From a conservative position, Angela Merkel was criticized as a figure that split the EU further ("Spalterin"/"splitter") (AT-2018-P3). Her liberal approach to allowing refugees to travel to Germany in 2015 created stronger divisions between eastern and western Member States. Viktor Orban by contrast is used as the prime example of a certain type of right-wing populism that swept Europe since the crisis of 2015.

7.2 Political targets and domestic audiences

There is a broad variety of different understandings about who were the audiences of domestic and European Home Affair policies.

Authors from the conservative *Die Presse* (AT-2018-P4, AT-2017-P5) argued that it was widely considered politically incorrect to distinguish between refugees and immigrants, and also stated that asylum seekers should not be able to freely choose their destination country in the EU. Another commentator (AT-2015-P7) pointed out how even the European director of UNHCR, Vincent Cochetel, spoke of economic migrants who were "blocking the [asylum] system" amidst the "welcoming culture" of 2015. He argued that this understanding reached wider public circles, once it became clear that European countries would not be able to admit so many people. The article is exemplary for the argument whereby "bogus" refugees had to be stopped or returned more efficiently in order to make space for "genuine" refugees.

An author of the liberal *Standard* (AT-2018-ST2) believed that the political assumption that a decent treatment of refugees only attracted new immigrants "was poisonous to any community". The commentator from (AT-2015-ST6) pointed to the need to protect vulnerable refugees, and enable legal channels for migrants who were striving to realise their talents in Europe. Likewise, another author from *Standard* (AT-2015-ST7) criticized the juxtaposition between refugee groups of 2015 and those of the early 1990s. Arguably, public discourse would often display the argument whereby refugees of the 1990s from the Balkans did not pose a problem because they "were like us", whereas new refugees "are all Muslims or black" and were thus not compatible with Austrian society. He asks "[h]ow can one convey to the [Viennese] coffee house community that persons who were forced to flee were people who wanted nothing else but the recognition of their rights and nothing more than to participate in this world on an equal footing?" (AT-2015-ST7) Evidently, the Viennese "coffee house community" is considered

ST1 argues: “But it’s not that simple. The refugees are a comparatively minor problem - besides the financial, banking and euro crisis, besides the job misery, besides the threat of war and terror. A lot of things are projected onto them.”

Another commentator seeks to rebut the assumption of liberal naïveté: “Of course, nobody should be naïve. Immigration brings problems. There are people with partly bad education. Not everyone will find work, not everyone will integrate. People will come, including those who bring attitudes that do not match those of a liberal society ranging from equality between men and women to anti-Semitic prejudices and hatred of Jews. A liberal society must face up to this and must not show false tolerance, otherwise it will be undermined from within” (AT-2018-ST3).

Concerning the construction of domestic audiences, there is a general undercurrent that impinges on the Austrian population living in a time of uncertainty, which is related to both socio-economic conditions of post-financial-crisis Europe and the threat of terrorism related to cultural conflicts.

An author from *Presse* (AT-2015-P2) attempted to rebut the widely spread myth that Austrians used to be more tolerant to immigration in former decades. Arguably, they say, this would be a type of storytelling that euphemised a country’s history. By contrast, he describes liberal discourses whereby European asylum policies were “outrageous” or “pathetic” as “not always helpful”. He went on to offer a repeatedly presented argument whereby domestic perceptions of migration were divided by a cultural cleavage with highly-educated social strata not taking seriously the fears of less educated groups.

A commentator from *Standard* points out that domestic electorates were generally sceptical towards migration, but that cultural distance and supranational imposition of rules represented two critical aspects which further aggravated conflicts. He argued: “It is difficult enough for many citizens to accept immigration from within the EU, but few people want to leave the question of whether migrants from other cultures can come to the country to [the discretion of] Brussels” (AT-2015-ST1).

Similarly, another commentator points out: “At the latest after the New Year’s Eve in Cologne, support for migration from the Islamic world fell dramatically, the terrorist attacks in Paris and Brussels did their part. With the resistance against the asylum policy, euro-scepticism grew, and it probably weakened the EU even more than the euro crisis” (AT-2018-ST2).

In summary, when it comes to the construction of policy targets, we find at least two different interpretations regarding the discursive division between immigrants who are considered deserving of protection and those who are not. In the conservative newspaper, we find arguments legitimizing the distinction between “bogus refugees” and refugees that are viewed to be genuinely in need of help. Thereby, the authors point out how one group prevents the other from having a fast asylum procedure and receiving broader societal support. By contrast, authors in the liberal newspaper issue critique about the same arguments of playing out groups and generations of immigrants against each other. Instead, we find a plea in favour of legal channels of labour immigration. In relation to domestic audiences, both liberal and conservative stances seek to provide explanations regarding the electorate that is sceptical towards immigration.

7.3 Making sense of policy legacy and calling for reforms

A widely shared undercurrent is that some member states, most notably Germany but also Italy and Austria, pursued variations of a naïve “welcoming politics” in the early months of 2015. Now they would wake up to the real challenges of curbing future immigration and integrating those who have already been admitted.

Two authors of *Kurier* (AT-2015-K5) used the title “We can make it! Can we?” (“Wir schaffen das! Schaffen wir das?”) referring to Angela Merkel’s infamous slogan and questioning it at the same time. They point out how the real challenge starts with the organisation of integration, education, employment and housing for refugees.

Generally, calls for tightened external border controls can be found across both conservative and liberal media. An author from *Die Presse* (AT-2015-P1) referred to the fact that national border fences were erected in response to refugee influx in 2015 and 2016 as “absurd”. According to him, European border policies have failed. A possible solution would be a further delegation of sovereignty to the EU with regard to the protection of external borders. Another commentator from *Presse* (AT-2015-P6) takes an even harsher stance, arguing that the EU should stop having moral doubts about protecting its external borders:

This makes it all the more disconcerting how the EU and individual Member States, in the face of the increasingly visible migration fiasco, are whistling away at yesterday’s morality buzz and doing exactly what the Americans have been accused of for decades. In their aimlessness and need, the Europeans seek the alliance with Turkey of the would-be Sultan Recep Tayyip Erdoğan (AT-2015-P6).

By contrast, a commentator from the liberal *Standard* (AT-2018-ST2) argued in favour of tightening external border protection with the rationale of saving refugee lives. He concluded that “all plans of this kind, be they refugee centres in North Africa or in Albania, can be strongly criticised. But it is then necessary to explain how the incentive to enter the EU by sea can be removed in another way. For one thing has been learned since 2015, that is, liberal asylum policy endangers liberal society.”

A commentator from *Kurier* (AT-2019-K1) detects a heavy burden on the Member States along the EU’s external borders. He argued that it is understandable that Greece, Italy and Spain feel left alone in the face of lacking solidarity to share burdens in other Member States. Thus, he goes on to demand more cooperation with African countries for origin. Arguably, people from West Africa would seldom receive asylum, thus it would be important to enable more efficient returns. A similar argument is shared by a commentator from *Presse* (AT-2018-P4).

It is however also interesting to see that it is not only authors in liberal media who proposed some kind of distribution policy, yet in the following example, the main rationale was that asylum seekers should not be able to choose their destination country. The author from *Presse* (AT-2018-P4) considered it a central issue that asylum seekers would have a chance to choose their destination country. What is needed according to him was a stronger harmonization of asylum procedures, rights, duties and reception systems for asylum seekers.

8. Responses of Project Stakeholders

8.1 Calling for European solidarity

Among the stakeholders that we interviewed for this project,⁶ there was a large consensus regarding the role of the European Union for the governance of migration and asylum. Almost all of our interlocutors pointed out that the Union was supposed to be a project of solidarity, where Member States supported each other in the governance of refugee protection. Accordingly, more competences should be delegated to the European level as Member States only seem to be pursuing their individual interests (E06). The current approach, most notably the Dublin Regulation would lead to a high pressure on external border Member States like Greece, Spain or Italy that feel abandoned by the rest of the Union. Classical central- and northern European destinations such as Austria, Germany and Sweden by contrast, would point to their fulfilled duties during 2015 and 2016 when they admitted a considerable share of asylum seekers.

Austria is argued to have taken a highly restrictive stance on migration and asylum since 2015. This is effectively mirrored by the recent laws such as the introduction of temporary asylum, whose only purpose is to render refugees insecure (E07). Furthermore, federal level politicians were said to actively signal a restrictive stance on immigration by introducing border controls or announcing that they would make Austria unattractive for immigrants. This broad public perception was particularly coined by the early arrival of a right-wing coalition in government in 2018. However, many of our interlocutors contrasted the federal government's approach to that of single provinces and municipalities. According to some of our interview partners, many politicians, bureaucrats and members of civil society at the sub-national level would be genuinely interested in solving policy, irrespective of their political ideology.

8.2 Making sense of refugee depictions in media and politics

A widely shared impression among our interlocutors was that the presence of refugees was highly politicized in media were a highly politicized societal group, despite a significant drop in the number of newly arriving asylum by the time of the interviews. Arguably, federal level politics would insist that “the country is changing radically because of many refugees” (E01 citing dominant political attitudes). In an attempt to cater to right-wing constituents, differences would be politically used by government actors to further emphasize a division between immigrants and the rest of society (E08). According to E07, prejudices even reach into court rooms, where asylum seekers appealing negative asylum decisions were confronted with judges with their own preconceptions about their trustworthiness based on the country of origin.

Media, particularly tabloids would furthermore have a tendency to negatively depict refugees, with either as a problem in the most general sense or as criminals in the worst case (E06). E02 argues: “because of the extremely negative, very one-sided reporting in the media, it is also very difficult to present a reasonable picture, even if it is not so rosy. I have the feeling that you either want to have these flowery reports from some asylum seeker who graduated with 1.0 at

⁶ See a list of all interviewed experts and their affiliation in the appendix.

university and is super integrated and speaks perfect German. Or you would like to have these ‘Oh now an asylum seeker has raped someone and this now confirms our picture’”.

One of our interviewees (E08) argued that “refugees are currently seen as a disruptive factor in our society. They are not welcome and it is assumed that they do not want to adapt at all. By integration I think the average voter, who elected this government understands that “[the refugees] have to adapt totally. Then they would be integrated.” I believe that the average Austrian expects 100% adaptation to our living conditions”.

In this context, another stakeholder (E05) compared the dominant integration paradigm with a “hurdle race”, whereby all eyes are placed on newly arrived refugees that are supposed to perform well in terms of language acquisition, employment, or acquiring cultural codes. The expert juxtaposes these assumptions with everyday work experiences and states that “there is no homogeneous native group and no homogeneous immigrant group. And if these groups do not exist, then I cannot pretend that they do. Perhaps politics can do that, but I can’t. I work with individuals [...] We start from individuals and speak of intersectionality in counselling. I don’t look one-dimensionally: you are a Turk, you are Bosnian, you are Syrian, but you are an old or young man with this or that educational experience, with this or that socialization, etc. And all these different dividing lines and affiliations make sense for inclusion work. Then I know much more” (E05).

8.3 Demanding policy reform: ending Dublin and introducing an EU distribution mechanism

Among the stakeholders in our sample, there was a broad consensus that the EU is in urgent need of asylum policy reforms. Most of them bemoaned many Member States’ restrictive approach of “we are closing down” (E01), not only for ideological reasons but also because they consider it an unrealistic approach. Arguably, it is not possible to shut off Europe from the rest of the world, even if the EU currently seeks to externalize migration control and refugee reception to third countries. Several interlocutors echoed debates over a race to the bottom. Arguably, Member States would try to outdo each other by formulating ever more restrictive policies.

Our experts expressed that the EU and its Member States needed to take up responsibility for refugee protection and establish mechanisms that fairly distributed societal costs, associated with providing protection. In this regard, many of our interlocutors expressed frustration over the Dublin Regulation, which would reinforce an unfair distribution of asylum seekers in Europe. Instead they called for European dispersal policies and a stronger harmonization of asylum procedures and reception systems. Despite the existence of a Common European Asylum System, many felt that in practice, there were considerable disparities with regard to procedural outcomes and reception conditions.

9. Conclusions

This working paper has explored various interpretations of the EU as a polity and as a set of rules, beliefs and cultures envisioned by Austrian political and media actors, as well as experts working in the field of asylum.

Overall, there are two broad lines of argumentation relating to understandings of immigration and policy reform which both lead to different visions of the EU. On the conservative spectrum, the EU is largely envisioned as a project that advances national self-interest to the supranational level. It is considered a power container against unwanted consequences of a globalized world in which states are struggling to maintain control over immigration. At the Member State level, Germany's Angela Merkel is frequently referred to as negative example of naïve liberal immigration policy. The so-called refugee crisis of 2015/2016 is considered an example of failure of existing governance arrangements, mostly by pointing to failed return policies or asylum seekers' agency in choosing their destination country. In this context, political and media actors tend to problematize related policy target groups as economic, illegal, or irregular migrants rather than refugees. Humanitarian obligations are partly denied by pointing to safe third countries in the EU neighbourhood or, in the most extreme cases, they are considered as part of a moral hypocrisies preventing the EU from becoming a sovereign actor in protecting its borders.

On the liberal spectrum, human rights are placed at the centre of attention and the main question is how the EU can practically serve these rights and ensure the protection and wellbeing of refugees. The crisis of 2015/2016 is considered as a crisis resulting from Member States' self-interested actions and an insufficiently harmonized Common European Asylum System. In this context, Hungary's Viktor Orban is negatively referred to as an example of right-wing populism that has been sweeping through Europe in recent years and that erodes the rule of law in the EU. Political and media actors tend to emphasize the vulnerability of immigrants as persons, who are fleeing war, persecution and exploitation. They partly address scepticism towards immigration among the domestic population but they tend to interpret it as a class struggle, whereby lower social classes are argued to be losers of globalization that are competing with immigrants. Finally, they favour active distribution and integration policies but show ambivalence regarding cooperation with third countries in the EU neighbourhood (i.e. EU-Turkey deal).

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Appendix

Example of coded claims in political speech analysis

Categories of Analysis	Sub-Categories	Codes for claims
Polity	EU	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU abolished itself • EU as an inevitable democratic reality • EU as venue shopping • EU has to change to prevail • EU Turkey cooperation necessary • Fortifying borders contradicts European and Humanitarian idea • Lack of Solidarity for external MS led to EU crisis • Liberal democracy as central idea for EU • Nationalist policies oppose the idea of unified EU • No delegation of sovereignty due to past integration failures • North-South divide or first-second class members • Refugee crisis triggered EU crisis • Solidarity among MS required • Subsidiarity as principle for future development
	Member State (MS)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Austria as a restrictive state • Austria as a state with strong humanitarian stance or tradition • Austria self-responsible for crisis • Austrian cooperation with Western Balkans states • Austrian role in EU: acknowledge diverse opinions and mediate • EU crisis necessitates national measures • Exploitation of welfare state leads to disintegration • Member state only calls for EU if affected itself • National borders constitutive of state
Actors	Object (talked about)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Threat to public order • They have different values • Smugglers decide who is coming to Europe • Religious and potentially radical • Refugees' vulnerability, in need of help • Refugees flee from terrorists (too) • Need to be integrated • Migrants as part of country's history • Long term migrants don't see themselves as Austrians • Economic refugees block the asylum system • Coming illegally • Bogus asylum seeker • Benefit seeking EU citizens • Asylum seekers must show solidarity with Austria • People's (electorate's) worries and fears are real
	Subject (talked to)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Politicians talk has impact on actions • 'We' are morally and legally obliged to help • We must not allow migrants exploit our legal system • 'We' must not tolerate intolerance • 'We' need common values • 'We' need to express expectations of liberal society • We with western way of life are threatened by terrorism
Policy Propositions	Diagnosis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Abuse of right to asylum or hiding of identity • Accommodation forms for asylum seekers • Asylum seekers committing crimes • Crisis management 2015 failed • Different values and deviance • Economic migrants in the asylum system

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU-Citizens with disproportionate social benefits in Austria • Lack of development aid • Length of asylum procedure • National admission capacities have been reached • Permeable external borders and major entry routes • Root causes and external aid situation
	Prognosis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Wage protection against EU-citizens • Social benefits for ben. of asylum and asylum seekers • Securitization of borders • Sea rescue missions • Providing protection • Involvement of EU neighbourhood • Foster integration efforts • Fair trade policies • Effective return policy • Distribution of asylum seekers across EU • Create legal entrance routes for asylum seekers • Combat asylum abuse

Experts interviewed for the RESPOND WP1-6

	Main field of expertise	Type of institution	Work profile
Vienna			
E01	Reception/ Integration	NGO	Administrative & practical
E02	Reception	NGO	Administrative & practical
E03	Reception/ Integration	NGO	Practical
E06	Integration	Public administration	Administrative
E08	Reception	Public administration	Administrative
Upper Austria			
E04	Reception/Integration	NGO	Administrative & practical
E05	Reception/Integration	NGO	Administrative
E10	Reception/Integration	Local government	Administrative
E12	Reception/Integration	Public administration	Administrative & practical
National level			
E07	Refugee protection monitoring	NGO	Administrative
E09	Border management	Academia / Federal administration	Administrative
E11	Q&A: refugee protection and border management	Federal Ministry of Interior	Administrative

Selected newspaper articles

	Online edition of newspaper	Date	Headline
K1	Kurier	07.2019	<p>EU needs a new migration policy</p> <p>The distribution proposal of the future head of the Commission is correct, but it falls short of the mark.</p> <p><i>EU braucht eine neue Migrationspolitik</i></p> <p><i>Der Verteilungsvorstoß der künftigen Chefin der Kommission ist richtig, greift aber zu kurz.</i></p>
K2	Kurier	05.2015	<p>EU asylum policy is a disgrace for Europe</p> <p>Many rich countries continue to cowardly pull in their heads. We should shame them with more humanity.</p> <p><i>Asylpolitik der EU ist eine Schande für Europa</i></p> <p><i>Viele reiche Länder ziehen weiter feige den Kopf ein. Wir sollten sie mit mehr Menschlichkeit beschämen.</i></p>
K3	Kurier	06. 2015	<p>In the EU, the law of the jungle is back in force. Orban's goulash populism prevails. A defeat for model countries of humanity and asylum like Austria.</p> <p><i>In der EU herrscht wieder das Faustrecht. Orbans Gulasch-Populismus obsiegt. Eine Niederlage für die Humanität – und Asyl-Vorzeigeländer wie Österreich.</i></p>
K4	Kurier	03.2016	<p>Is the EU breaking up?</p> <p><i>Zerbricht die EU?</i></p>
K5	Kurier	09.2015	<p>We can do it! Can we do it?</p> <p>Thousands of refugees have applied for asylum in Austria. But the real tour de force is just beginning.</p> <p><i>Wir schaffen das! Schaffen wir das?</i></p> <p><i>Tausende Flüchtlinge haben in Österreich um Asyl angesucht. Der wahre Kraftakt beginnt aber erst.</i></p>
K6	Kurier	06.2018	<p>EU migration crisis: "Borders tight" is not yet a solution</p> <p>Many ideas, many catchwords - but the EU is far from a common solution to the migration issue.</p> <p><i>EU-Migrationskrise: „Grenzen dicht“ ist noch keine Lösung</i></p> <p><i>Viele Ideen, viele Schlagworte – aber von einer gemeinsamen Lösung ist man in der EU in der Migrationsfrage weit entfernt.</i></p>
K7	Kurier & Profil	07.2018	<p>Denial of reality</p> <p>Austria, the EU Council Presidency, is obviously not serious about preventing illegal immigration. Otherwise, Kurz & Co. would have to push ahead with concepts for legal migration under high pressure.</p> <p><i>Realitätsverweigerung</i></p> <p><i>Dem EU-Ratsvorsitz Österreich ist es offenbar nicht ernst damit, illegale Zuwanderung zu verhindern. Andernfalls müssten Kurz & Co. mit Hochdruck Konzepte für legale Migration vorantreiben.</i></p>
P1	Die Presse	12.2015	<p>At the limits of community capability</p> <p><i>An den Grenzen der Gemeinschaftsfähigkeit</i></p>
P2	Die Presse	08.2015	<p>Myths and reality of our helpfulness</p> <p><i>Mythen und Realität unserer Hilfsbereitschaft</i></p>

P3	Die Presse	02.2018	Merkel must go! Balanced appreciation of a splitter <i>Merkel muss weg! Abwägende Würdigung einer Spalterin</i>
P4	Die Presse	01.2018	European Family: Together strong - or weak <i>Europäische Familie: Gemeinsam stark – oder aber schwach</i>
P5	Die Presse	07.2017	Wie Migrationspolitik die EU-Staaten spaltet <i>How migration policy divides the EU states</i>
P6	Die Presse	11.2015	Europe's moral imperialism belongs in the dump <i>Europas Moral-Imperialismus gehört auf den Müllplatz</i>
P7	Die Presse	10.2015	The mind must precede the feeling <i>Der Verstand muss dem Gefühl vorgeschaltet sein</i>
ST1	Der Standard	11.2015	There is no simple solution Europe is overwhelmed by crises, refugees are the lesser problem <i>Es gibt keine einfache Lösung</i> <i>Europa ist mit Krisen vielfach überfordert, Flüchtlinge sind das kleinere Problem</i>
ST2	Der Standard	06.2018	What speaks in favor of a "Fortress Europe" from a liberal perspective <i>Was aus liberaler Sicht für eine "Festung Europa" spricht</i>
ST3	Der Standard	06.2018	A "Fortress Europe" will not stop right-wing populists <i>Eine "Festung Europa" wird Rechtspopulisten nicht stoppen</i>
ST4	Der Standard	09.2018	Unity would be Europe's trump card Jean-Claude Juncker's State of the Union speech would have needed more passion <i>Einigkeit wäre Europas Trumpf</i> <i>Jean-Claude Junckers Rede zur Lage der Union hätte mehr Leidenschaft gebraucht</i>
ST5	Der Standard	08.2016	New Enlightenment: Where is the EU soft power? <i>Neue Aufklärung: Wo ist die EU-Soft-Power?</i>
ST6	Der Standard	10.2015	Europa zwischen Helfer und Heuchler In der Flüchtlingspolitik muss die EU endlich ihren Werten gerecht werden <i>Europe between helper and hypocrite</i> <i>The EU must finally live up to its values in refugee polic</i>
ST7	Der Standard	08.2015	There is a refugee in all of us Legal migration must be possible, the money going to the traffickers could be used and invested more sensibly <i>In uns allen steckt ein Flüchtling</i> <i>Legale Migration muss möglich sein, das an die Schlepper gehende Geld könnte sinnvoller eingesetzt und investiert werden</i>

Selected political speeches

	Politician	Date of speech	Political party	Ideological position
AT1	Sebastian Kurz	09/2017	ÖVP	Conservative
AT2	Christian Kern	01/2017	SPÖ	Social democratic
AT3	Eva Glawischnig-Piszek	04/2015	GREENS	Liberal left
AT4	Heinz Christian Strache	11/2015	FPÖ	Far right
AT5	Johanna Mikl-Leitner	10/2012	ÖVP	Conservative
AT6	Werner Faymann	05/2016	SPÖ	Social democratic
AT7	Herbert Kickl	01/2018	FPÖ	Far right
AT8	Christian Kern	06/2016	SPÖ	Social democratic
AT9	Sebastian Kurz	06/2018	ÖVP	Conservative
AT10	Sebastian Kurz	03/2017	ÖVP	Conservative
AT11	Johanna Mikl-Leitner	06/2015	ÖVP	Conservative
AT12	Herbert Kickl	06/2018	FPÖ	Far right
AT13	Heinz-Christian Strache	12/2017	FPÖ	Far right
AT14	Werner Faymann	11/2015	SPÖ	Social democratic
AT15	Alev Korun	11/2015	GREENS	Liberal left